

Exploring Adolescence and Identity in Ted Dawe's *Trilogy*

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Abstract

Adolescence is a distinct and complex phase of life. The young adults, in search of their identity and freedom, make choices and develop new perspectives as they go out into the ‘real’ world. The present paper focuses on the phase of adolescence to bring out the dilemmas and identity crisis faced by these young minds especially through the main character of Ted Dawe’s trilogy—*Into the River*, *Into the World* and *Thunder Road*. Te Arepa/Devon, the main character of the trilogy unchains himself from school and family ties. The erroneous choices he opts for lead to his downfall. Te Arepa is not just a character in Dawe’s trilogy but he is a representative of many adolescents who find it difficult to resolve their identity crisis. The paper also tries to affirm the need for communication and understanding in relationships so that challenges can be faced by young adults with an indomitable spirit.

Keywords: Adolescence, Young Adults, Identity, Communication, Society

Adolescence is defined as a period that begins with the physical changes of puberty and lasts until roughly age 20 (Carver and Scheier 294). The word “adolescence” comes from the Latin term *adolescere* which means to become established or to mature as a plant does (Coats ch. 1). This is a complicated phase in the lives of teenagers who question various aspects of society and also try to decipher their own identity as an individual. They begin to see things through a different lens as they move out into the real world. During this complex phase of growing up, a prominent concern is the identity formation. Identity can refer to the specific characteristics or beliefs that distinguish an individual/people from others. Identity can be personal identity which includes “a subjective sense of continuous existence and a coherent memory” whereas psychosocial identity is “at once subjective and objective, individual and social” (Erikson 61). Biological factors, cultural communities, family, physical environment, society—all of these affect the identity formation of an individual.

Ted Dawe, a writer from New Zealand, has won many awards for his literary works for children and young adults. A daring writer—he has the grit to bring before the society the issues which the society chooses to overlook. In his works, we are introduced to an explicit depiction of the young generation indulging in drugs, drinking, sex and violent bullying. He is bold enough to lay bare before the readers, these disturbing issues through his enticing novels. Ted Dawe's trilogy that consists of *Into the River* (2012), *Into the World* (2016) and *Thunder Road* (2003) has been taken up for study in this paper. The trilogy revolves around the characters who are young adults—the adolescents who are in search of their identity and freedom. These youngsters gain new experiences, make decisions and choices as they develop new perspectives of the world. This paper dwells on the identity crisis of the main character of the trilogy, Te Arepa/Devon, who not only represents serious concerns of Ted Dawe about an individual but about the young generation in general. Te Arepa is just one young adult who vacillates in making correct choices but he is representative of the teenagers who at times feel stuck in their lives and may take the wrong path owing to unresolved conflicts or lack of association with their family and community. Te Arepa, the protagonist of Ted Dawe's trilogy, makes a choice of relieving himself from school and family ties. Caught in the web of illusion of freedom, he makes other misleading choices too. Being disconnected with his community and family, he makes impulsive choices and goes away forever. He is back with his family in his native place at the age of nineteen only as a dead body for funeral rites. The trajectory of the life of Te Arepa is traced by Dawe as in his trilogy he unfolds the emotional turbulence faced by adolescents in the bumpy teenage ride.

The identity formation during adolescence is of prime importance. A young adult who is able to resolve the conflicts faced during this period can develop into a healthy personality. It can become problematic and lead to a troubled identity if the mind remains unclear and conflicts unresolved. Erik Erikson, a well-known psychologist, propounded the psychosocial theory of identity. Erikson's theory brings forth the idea that all human beings pass through specific phases of development and in each stage of life there is a specific crisis or conflict between competing tendencies (Baron and Kalsher 336). The most crucial stage in Erikson's theory is that of adolescence which is marked by "the crisis of identity versus role confusion" (336). As these fragile young minds are toiling to understand their own existence and individuality, they question themselves: "Who am I? 'What am I really like?' 'What do I want to become?'" (336). It is important for these adolescents to find constructive answers to these questions and if they are unsuccessful in finding them, it may lead to uncertainty in their lives as they will not be sure of where they want to go or what they wish to accomplish (336). An individual does not lead a solitary existence but is also affected by the society in which he/she lives. The psychosocial identity depends on "a complementarity of an inner synthesis in the individual and the role of integration in the group" (Erikson 61). There are some specific and unique traits of each individual but that alone does not lead to complete identity formation. The social factors also affect every individual and it is the fusion of the individual and social that marks identity formation. Erikson believes that "identity derives from a melding of private and social self-conceptions" (Carver and Scheier 294).

In Ted Dawe's trilogy, the question of identity formation of Te Arepa becomes a focal issue to understand the choices he makes and the decisions he takes. Book I of the trilogy, *Into the River*, introduces the protagonist, Te Arepa. He is a young Māori (indigenous people of New Zealand) boy who is closely associated with the history and traditions of his tribal community. Te Arepa's grandfather is Ra and he is closely connected to his native land and culture. He narrates tales of their native land and people to Te Arepa. Te Arepa is awarded a scholarship at a prestigious boarding school in Auckland and he moves to the city to pursue further studies. There he realises that he is not accepted into the circle with open arms as he is a Māori. He faces bullying and has an identity conflict (Māori-White conflict). To fit into the circle, he decides to hide his Māori identity and even changes his name to Devon from Te Arepa. Being in the real world, out from the comfort of home, he comes to know about real-life politics and also drugs. Though he is a brilliant lad, good in studies, he begins making some impulsive choices that mislead him. It seems that he is not able to sort out his identity conflicts. Identity crisis can be defined as a "crucial time" for intensively exploring oneself and it is "an inescapable turning point for better or for worse" (Erikson 63). If there is an unresolved notion of self, the adolescents "may turn their back on many of the ethical, moral, economic, political or religious values held by the important people in their lives" and they "suffer from anxieties" (Bhatia 72). Te Arepa gets involved in drugs and makes other impulsive decisions. All this leads to his expulsion from school along with his friends. When he is being taken to the bus depot to be sent back home, he makes another impulsive decision and jumps out from the car yelling "Libertad" (Dawe 270, *Into the River*). He decides not to go back home and exclaims that he has made a choice of freedom.

Drug addiction, dropping out of school, activism and running away from schools are all different forms of "negative identity" (Bhatia 72). Te Arepa's indulging in drugs, being expelled from school and deciding not to return home are choices that make the young Te Arepa more susceptible to the dangerous world outside. He fails to develop a strong identity and keeps taking impulsive decisions without talking to even Ra. After his expulsion from school, he lands in the dark depths of the underworld and drugs. "Te Arepa's intelligent but confused emotional inner world grapples with the issues behind the sex and drug use" and the narrative explores "the precarious nature of the development of an adolescent boy" (Original Classification 11). There is constant strife in Te Arepa's heart and mind between his Māori identity and new city life of the boarding. As Te Arepa becomes more comfortable in city life, his attachment to his native place diminishes manifold. There is a yearning for freedom and a streak of rebellion accompanied by casual sexual encounters and drug abuse that define Te Arepa's life now as he is away from Ra and his community. He feels that Ra does not understand the importance and intricacy of fitting into the circle in the urban city school even if it has to be at the cost of loss of his real Māori identity. He had on one occasion talked to Ra about it and Ra was not happy with Te Arepa shadowing his real name and substituting it for Devon. Te Arepa comes from a home where the ill mother is at the hospital and the father is in prison. This too can be considered as a factor that to some extent hampers his ability to resolve the crisis as there is lack of communication with any of the family members and he keeps

making impetuous and hasty choices all by himself. The lack of bonding and communication with family can adversely affect the identity of an individual.

Many psychosocial factors may result in severe disturbances of the individual sense of identity (alienation, identity confusion, depersonalization) (Erikson 62). Identity confusion/identity diffusion is a “dominant feature in developmental disturbances in adolescence” (62). If an individual is unable to form an integrated or consolidated identity, it leads to “role confusion” which means that there is an absence of direction in one’s “sense of self” (Carver and Scheier 294). Anxiety and confusion can lead to adolescents becoming alienated or they may become extremely rebellious and indulge in violent behaviour. Violence can erupt in many ways and involves hurting, damaging or debilitating someone or something. Violence does not only cause physical damage to an individual but can be emotionally traumatic as well. Acts of violence like bullying, sexual abuse and killings also lead to psychological violence and these scars can bring marked changes in the personality of an individual.

Te Arepa, the boy with a high potential to rise in life, decides to traverse dark paths of the underworld in company of his friend Mitch. He decides to contact his school friend, Mitch rather than returning to his native place after he is expelled from school. Mitch now works for Rebel who is a drug dealer and a veteran of many illegal activities. Devon gets caught up in the quagmire when he goes out in the car with Mitch and other two rowdy men, Hooks and Muttley. Hooks and Muttley had just been released from prison and they go around openly and violently robbing and raping. Devon does not want to be a part of this violence but stays with them because of his friend, Mitch. Devon “watched all of this dumbstruck. What looked bad from the beginning was now unspeakably worse. And he was part of it” (Dawe ch. 18, *Into the World*). Devon did not like their violent activities but he stays with them for Mitch and therefore makes an erroneous choice. He is not directly involved in any of their violent illegal activities but being with them makes him an offender. Devon has to pay the price for his faltered choices and he lands in prison.

Devon suffers from identity confusion. He knows that he is averse to these kinds of violent activities and he even wants to part away from these violent men but he is unable to make a smart choice. Being with Mitch, caught up in the company of underworld men after being expelled from school worsens his identity woes. Young adults like Devon who are suffering from identity diffusion may become aimless in their pursuits and “this situation produces a prolonged adolescence marked by uncertainty and lack of commitment” (Bhatia 71). Failure to achieve a meaningful sense of personal identity can result in juvenile delinquency as happens in the case of Devon (Mussen et al. 417). He gets involved with the underworld gangs and their activities. In adolescents, the quest for identity is extremely pertinent as “they adopt many different strategies to help them resolve their own personal identity crises” (Baron and Kalsher 336). If these young minds fail to resolve their crisis, the outcome can be a tormented identity with lack of direction in life.

Life gives Devon a second chance as he is recommended to pursue his further studies through a Correction Programme for young offenders. Devon resumes his studies and does a course in journalism and later becomes an intern at the *Tribune* which is owned by Wes. He behaves well and is also appreciated at the *Tribune* during his internship. Devon is taken in custody by this rich old man, Wes. Initially Devon follows rules stated by Wes during his stay at Wes' place but soon he begins to take liberty in certain matters which is unacceptable to Wes. Wes threatens to send Devon back to prison as he feels that Devon is acting rebelliously and not adhering to the rules while staying at his place. Devon does not want to be bound within the walls of the prison again and plans to outplay Wes. He collects all the secret data from Wes' system with the help of an IT professional. Devon finds unpleasant images of innocent kids in his system apart from data of notorious people who time and again come to meet Wes at his place. Devon assertively tells Wes to let him go away without creating any hassle or he would make Wes' secrets public and defame him. Wes is trapped and has no choice but to let Devon go away. Devon relocates to the boarding house of Thunder Road to live his life without inhibitions. Again, with his distorted sense of comprehension of freedom, Devon plunges into the world of goons which revolves around many illegal activities involving money, dangerous street racing and drugs.

Society plays an important part in the life of an individual who is governed by its rules and norms. The rules/norms that govern a society are never stagnant and reforms or changes keep happening over the years. Though all norms may not be correct from one's perspective and need to be interrogated, there are others that are in the best interest of the society at large. Dealing in the underworld and being involved in drug activities is risky and illegal and can in no way be considered to be right. The youngsters can fall an easy prey to taking drugs or getting involved in certain illegal activities. "As all teenagers can be risk-takers to some degree, taking things to extremes can be influenced by the company they keep" and this is what exactly happens with Trace (Bennett et al, 32 Teenagers). Trace is Devon's roommate at the boarding house of Thunder Road. He is a small town boy who is introduced to the big city life and its ways by Devon. Trace accompanies Devon for street racing too and is influenced by him to be a party to some illegal and risk-taking activities. Devon works as a reporter but he also goes for street racing at Thunder Road which is otherwise prohibited as it is risky and dangerous. It is in this area that at night other illegal activities also go on. Trace has a passion for bikes and cars and in no time, he becomes a party to the Thunder Road visits along with Devon. They smoke joint together and soon Devon lets out other plans to Trace which he says would make them rich. Devon plans to indulge in dope/drug business and Trace agrees to become a partner in Devon's illegal enterprise.

Devon and Trace get involved in selling drugs in the underworld. They land in a precarious situation as they are questioned about their secret drug dealing activities by Sloane whose power and authority is acknowledged at Thunder Road by all those who deal there. Devon and Trace are constantly gripped by a feeling of fear. Devon's erroneous choice of this life ultimately leads to his death as Sloane, Wes' son, ends his sport with Devon. Devon suffers a fatal accident as he is escaping from the goons in a high speeding car. After being taken to the hospital, Devon stays in coma for some time but eventually dies. Trace too is not spared by

the goons and he meets with a bike accident as they follow him. Trace is hurt and receives treatment at the hospital where he recuperates.

Not only those young adults who have gone off track are risk-takers but all teenagers can to some extent indulge in risk-taking. Many youngsters in Dawe's trilogy go to Thunder Road to prove their mettle in the dangerous game of car racing. Devon goes far ahead in risk taking and his dealing in drugs that spoil lives or indulging in underworld activities lead to unpleasant consequences.

Being connected with the family, discussing things and paying attention to words of wisdom of the older people can help the adolescents in overcoming their confusions. Te Arepa dismisses Ra's advice and breaks away his ties with his community. Te Arepa was a talented boy with good intellect and writing skills but peer pressure, not listening to Ra's advice, his disconnectedness with his roots and his inability to resolve his identity confusion—all lead to his downfall.

Ra is sometimes seen to be too glued in his Māori traditions but as an adult he knows quite a lot about the real world and its ways. Ra encourages Te Arepa to join the boarding school in Auckland and is enthusiastic about Te Arepa going out to city for a good education. Ra wants his grandson to transform into a responsible citizen who would contribute to society in a constructive way. Ra had thought that by sending him to a good school, he could keep away Te Arepa from the local boys, many of whom indulge in drugs or become a part of gangs. Camouflaged into Devon Santos from Te Arepa to hide his Māori identity, Te Arepa makes misinformed choices and ultimately Ra's hopes are quashed.

Adolescence brings with it many challenges. If family and school connections break down, affirmation is found elsewhere by these teenagers and they may even become part of criminal gangs as does Te Arepa. Communication thus becomes an essential tool to mend to strained relationships. Adults need to talk to the adolescents without being judgmental. The voice of writers like Ted Dawe become poignant in today's world as they try to bring out the real challenges faced by these young minds. The young adults should not be pressurized to blindly follow the societal norms. If they have certain issues or questions, there should be an open room for discussion. They should be allowed to speak out about things affecting their lives in this age of emotional confusions. Listening to their point of view and chalking out strategies together to work out things can lead to healthy outcomes. The society will progress and grow constructively only if these young individuals are able to resolve their identity confusions, thus forming citizens with healthy personalities. The youngsters should grow up in a manner that fosters a strong sense of self that can help them to move on resiliently. They should be able to make informed decisions and not give in to wrong choices, no matter how tempting these may seem to be. Communication is like an umbilical cord between the adults and young adults and it should not be severed. Fruitful communication should go on, be it in daily conversation or even through books for young adults. In words of Karen Coats: "Young people are our only hope to save the world and make it a better place" (ch. 1).

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